

REMOTE CONNECTIONS AND REMOTE MONITORING OF MICROPROCESSOR SYSTEM PARAMETERS

Irgashev Nuriddin Normurod ugli

Assistant, Tashkent State University of Transport,
Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent

E-mail: Irgashev_nn@bk.ru

Ruzimov Otakhon Orifjon ugli

Assistant, Tashkent State University of Transport,
Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent

E-mail: ruzimov1125@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7966302>

ABSTRACT

This article discusses how to connect microcontrollers to a PLC and how to monitor microprocessors. Three different methods were considered as monitoring methods. The most reliable of the considered methods are recommended to be used in the processes of microprocessor monitoring. It shows how to use the recommended method in teaching processes and how to control microprocessors through the PLC.

Key words: PLC, VPN, Windows, macOS, Linux, LAN, WAN, IP, TCP, PPTP, DNS address, router, remote.

With the development of industrial technology, more and more equipment's, such as PLCs and industrial computers, are widely used in industrial places. A programmable logic controller (PLC), also known as a programmable controller, is a robust and durable digital computer that is used in industrial process control. Typically used on assembly lines, for the control and management of robotic devices, and in any industrial activity requiring a high degree of reliability. PLCs are usually relatively easy to program and can help diagnose process errors.

When an equipment error is detected, the equipment can be maintained and diagnosed remotely, reducing the time and cost of maintenance by engineers. Thus, remote diagnostics and maintenance are urgent problems that customers need to solve. Of course, there are many solutions to achieve remote access. Here, the author proposes solutions that use: TeamViewer software, VPN connection and the method of establishing a connection using a modem router to implement remote access to the PLC.

We will consider the above methods step by step in our work.

TeamViewer is a fast and secure remote management tool designed to help managed IT service providers proactively monitor remote systems, client endpoints and networks. It can monitor devices like Windows, macOS, and Linux

for early detection of issues. It helps team members stay connected from different locations through online meetings. TeamViewer consists of an intuitive and easy to use interface with powerful remote access features.

For PLC control software to be of any use, it needs network access. To provide this network connection, the Serial to Ethernet Connector software application is the ideal solution. This application has been developed to provide remote access to RS 232/485/422 interfaces. Using the software allows you to share any serial port on the network, whether it's LAN, WAN, or IP.

Remote PLC software virtualizes the computer's serial connections and allows access to serial devices connected to the network. This eliminates the need for a physical connection between the server and the hardware that needs to be accessed and managed.

Consider the following method using a VPN connection.

A VPN connection is a short form of a virtual private network that provides privacy, anonymity, and security on the public Internet. A VPN service masks the ISP's IP address, making online activities almost impossible to trace. A VPN can also be used to connect computers to isolated, remote computer networks that are not normally available using the Internet or other intervening network. Another use of a VPN is that client computers can browse websites through a VPN server even if they are on a restricted internal network.

The Routing and Remote Access Service is a proprietary Windows server role that supports connecting a remote user or site to a site using a virtual private network (VPN) or dial-up connections. Thus, using RRAS, we can convert a regular Windows server into a VPN server. Microsoft RRAS server and VPN client support VPN connection based on PPTP, L2TP/IPsec, SSTP and IKEv2.

By default, VPN connections are made using PPTP, which is a point-to-point VPN tunneling protocol. It is also possible to convert the VPN server to support SSTP. The PPTP connection is established on TCP port 1723. PPTP also uses GRE and supports encryption keys up to 128 bits. PPTP is a very fast VPN protocol that is easy to set up. It is supported by most operating systems such as Windows, Mac, Linux PC, as well as Android and IOS mobile devices.

The last method is the most primitive, but the most effective method of the above. One of the advantages of the method is that this connection method does not require additional devices for connecting remote access, except for a modem router with an Internet connection. It is required to configure the modem router, write IP addresses, and save the settings. After that, you can remotely connect to this IP address.

To further implement the method, the first step is to configure the modem router.

It is necessary to ensure that the router finds and reflects this controller in the list of connected devices. If the controller is not visible in the list of connected devices, then further configuration does not make sense since the routing rules specified in the router will not function.

It is necessary to preserve the static IP address of the PLC (should be in the DHCP address range), as well as the local DNS address with the MAC address. It is important not to forget to set the gateway address inside the PLC, that is, the local IP address of the router.

Thus, three main methods of establishing a connection and remote monitoring of a system are considered, focusing on the last method of implementing a connection.

Bibliography:

- 1.S.Rapuano and F. Zoino, «Система управления обучением по измерительному приборостроению», IEEE Transaction on Instrumentation & Measurements, vol. 55, No. 5, pp. 1757-1766, October 2006.
- 2.D.Grimaldi, S. Rapuano, T. Laoroulos, «Аспекты традиционной и виртуальной лаборатории для обучения приборостроению и измерениям», Proc. of the 22nd IEEE Instrumentation and Measurement Technology Conference 2005 (IEEE IMTC 2005), vol. 2, pp. 1233-1238, Ottawa (Canada), May 2005.
3. Иргашев Н.Н., Рузимов О.О. Цифровой мониторинг при дистанционном обучении // Universum: технические науки: электрон. научн. журн. 2023. 3(108).
4. Кангин В.В., Козлов В.Н. Аппаратные и программные средства систем управления. Промышленные сети и контроллеры: Учеб, пособие. М.: БИНОМ: Лаб. базовых знаний, 2010

